

Applying computational approaches to energy discourse: a comparative methodological study of rule-based and large language model qualitative content analysis

Abstract

In this article, my objective is to conduct a comparative analysis of a rule-based ontological classification tool and a large language model (LLM) chatbot as qualitative content analysis tools. The focus is on assessing their strengths and limitations when applied to the study of discourse surrounding the energy transition. To achieve this, I use the tools to analyse two different types of corpora: citizens' social media discussions and politicians' parliament speeches. In the analysis, I evaluate the differences in the methods' recall and precision levels. Additionally, I assess the extent to which these methods align with scientific principles, including reliability, transparency, and research integrity. The results reveal a classic trade-off: the LLM's precision is high, but its recall is comparatively low, suggesting its strength in generating accurate but potentially incomplete analyses. On the other hand, the rule-based method outperforms in recall at the expense of precision, capturing more data points but with varying accuracy levels. I discuss the implications of the results and outline ideas for leveraging the strengths of both methods in future studies. This article provides researchers with insights into the selection and application of computational tools in the social sciences and humanities, as well as in multifaceted research topics such as the energy transition.

1 Introduction

"Investments in the green transition are essential for our environment, economy, and security... Investments enable, for example, purchase and conversion subsidies for low-emission vehicles. We prevent mobility poverty by providing support and alternative modes of transportation to people."

A member of a government party at the Finnish parliament in June 2022

"The green transition has driven energy prices up... the government is pouring taxpayers' money into electric vehicle support... it has ripped off the money for the green overhaul at the expense of citizens' purchasing power and daily survival and put the state in disastrous debt."

An anonymous commenter on an online news site in January 2023

These comments extracted from my research data are examples of the multifaceted nature of the energy discourse and the contradictions between the views of citizens and politicians. The first comment supports the government's policy while the second opposes it. Studying discourses is an important part of understanding the energy transition from fossil fuels to renewable energy sources, as they are intertwined with prevailing energy practices and are at the same time important factors in explaining the change (Buschmann & Oels, 2019). My goal in this article is to consider feasible approaches for studying the energy discourse on a larger scale through thousands or even millions of comments from citizens and politicians. Analysing such large datasets qualitatively is challenging, if not impossible, for humans, so

they require the adoption of automated text analysis methods (Grimmer & Stewart, 2013; Van Atteveldt et al., 2019). In this article, I will employ two different approaches for the task and discuss their differences, as well as their strengths and limitations.

The utilisation and application of big data, artificial intelligence, and advanced computational methods continue to expand exponentially, reaching into new areas of research. Scholars from various fields, including social sciences and humanities, are exploring new methods to address complex societal challenges (Andreotta et al., 2019; Halford & Savage, 2017; Ziems et al., 2023). Among these challenges, one of the areas that have received considerable research attention is the energy transition. Researchers emphasize the significance of comprehensively studying all levels of decision-making in the energy sector, including sustainable policymaking and infrastructure planning (Radtke & Scherhauser, 2022). Furthermore, they underscore the importance of recognizing how energy-related decisions impact the daily lives and economic well-being of individual consumers (Ortiz et al., 2017; Steg et al., 2018). Being able to conduct large-scale qualitative data analysis to the discourse surrounding the energy sector is important given its multifaceted nature and influence on various stakeholders and societal structures.

Much of the previous NLP-powered energy transition research has focused on using unsupervised machine learning methods, specifically topic modeling, to uncover latent topics in the material (Dehler-Holland et al., 2021; Repo et al., 2021; Rizzoli et al., 2024; Saheb et al., 2022; Tie & Zhu, 2022). Alternatively, dictionary-based NLP has been employed to analyse specific aspects of data, such as gender perspectives (Carroll et al., 2024), the involvement of startups in renewable energy (Singh et al., 2021) and renewable energy investor sentiment (Herrera et al., 2022).

This study is part of a broader research project that involves extracting keywords and classifying a large dataset of Finnish energy discourse. The dataset comprises two subsets: online consumer discussions, characterized by a more general vocabulary, and politicians' parliamentary speeches, which approach the subject from a macro-level perspective and contain more specialized vocabulary. The purpose of using two different data sets in the research project is to gain a more comprehensive understanding of energy transition-related discussions, considering both the perspectives of everyday consumers and the rhetoric of policymakers. My objective in this article is to contribute a new methodological perspective to the field of energy transition research by evaluating the advantages and limitations of two NLP approaches to analysing the energy transition discourse: a large language model (LLM) and a rule-based ontological classification. I will now proceed to introduce these approaches in more detail.

LLMs offer numerous possibilities and prospects for academic research. ChatGPT is one of the tools that has attracted the most interest among researchers and the general public. Since OpenAI launched ChatGPT in November 2022, research articles using ChatGPT have been published at a rapid pace. Many of these studies have demonstrated that ChatGPT's performance in various tasks is comparable to that of humans in terms of quality. In a study by Huang et al. (2023), ChatGPT was able to identify implicit hate speech well compared to humans. Guo et al. (2023) found that ChatGPT's capabilities to answer questions from several domains including finance, medicine, law, and psychology, were on par with those of human

experts. Gilardi et al. (2023) reported that ChatGPT even outperformed humans in annotation tasks including relevance, stance, topics, and frames detection.

On the other hand, ChatGPT's ability to produce consistent results has been questioned and caution has been advised regarding its application to text classification (Reiss, 2023). Ziems et al., (2023) did an extensive evaluation to measure the zero-shot performance of 13 language models on 25 representative English CSS benchmarks and concluded that, except in a minority of cases, prompted LLMs did not match or exceed the performance of carefully fine-tuned classifiers, and the best LLM performance was often considered too low to fully replace human annotation. Some studies have found ChatGPT's zero-shot performance to be lacking, but prompt engineering and additional training have been shown to improve results (Shi et al., 2023; Yuan et al., 2023).

Although ChatGPT has been extensively examined for a diverse range of tasks, there remains a gap in empirical research regarding its utilisation as a classification tool in qualitative research in the energy sector. In addition, Finnish-language data have not been used as research material.

In this article, I will compare ChatGPT's performance as a classification tool with a traditional rule-based NLP tool called Etuma. The Etuma tool is based on dictionaries, grammar rules and ontologies, performing basic NLP tasks such as lemmatization as well as morphological, syntactical, semantic and sentiment analysis (Etuma 2023). In this article, I will especially focus on the part of Etuma's analysis process that uses ontologies for the classification. In the field of information processing and artificial intelligence, ontology refers to the description and definition of existence in a form that can be understood by a computer (Gruber, 1995, p. 908). Although ontologies may contain relatively generalizable information, which allows them to be reused for different purposes (Spyns et al., 2002), often they are employed in NLP tasks that require specialized knowledge and vocabulary (Khadir et al., 2021). Some studies have introduced ontologies developed for energy sector, such as Booshehri et al. (2021), Cuenca et al. (2020) and Küçük and Arslan (2014) for English and Glenc (2022) for Polish. To the best of my knowledge, a dedicated energy ontology for the Finnish language has not yet been developed, although a general Finnish ontology¹ does exist.

The study addresses the following research questions:

- 1) How do the rule-based ontological classification tool (Etuma) and the LLM chatbot (ChatGPT) differ as qualitative content analysis methods?
 - a. What kind of classification do they produce in a zero-shot setting?
 - b. How do recall and precision differ between the two methods and data sets?
- 2) How well do these methods align with scientific principles such as reliability and scientific integrity?

In the following section, I will describe the research materials, methods, and process. Then I will present and discuss the results and their limitations. I will conclude with insights and suggestions for future research.

¹ <https://finto.fi/yso/fi/>

2 Data

The corpus used for this study was originally collected for the broader research project focusing on analysing the energy discourse from the citizens' and politicians' perspectives. It consists of 110,295 social media comments from August 2022 to August 2023 and 25,872 parliament speeches from February 2022 to March 2023. The social media comments were collected using a web scraping tool called Mohawk Analytics (Legentic 2023) and the transcribed parliament speeches were downloaded from a database called Parliament Sampo (Hyvönen et al., 2022). For the purposes of this study, I limited the material to a smaller subset so that it would be easier to qualitatively assess the analysis results produced by each method. I employed a keyword search "electric car" AND "subsidy" ("sähköauto" AND "tuki" in Finnish) to filter texts discussing one of the topics that have caused disagreements between citizens and politicians, and which will be qualitatively analysed in the project: electric car subsidies offered by the Finnish government. The subset corpus contained 40 social media comments and 33 parliamentary speeches.

The social media data included 21 tweets from Twitter (currently X), 19 online news comments, and 4 discussion forum posts. The parliament speech corpus consisted of 13 speeches from the Finns party, 3 speeches from the Social Democratic party, 3 speeches from the Centre party, 3 speeches from the Green party, and one speech each from the National Coalition party and the Christian Democrats. In addition, the material included 5 responses from government ministers from the Social Democratic party, the Centre party, and the Green party. The original language of the texts was Finnish, but keywords, topics, and text quotes have been translated into English for this article. To clean the data, I removed mentions targeted to specific users (identified with the '@' character) in social media comments. I copied the original texts into an Excel file and recorded the analysis results obtained with different methods in their respective columns. Additionally, I randomly selected a sample for validating the results. I will describe the categorisation and validation processes in more detail in the following sections.

The social media comments were typically short, but their length varied between 20 and 155 words per comment. The comments were mostly critical towards the topic, as in statements like "*Electric car subsidies go to the wealthy and electricity subsidies also benefit the wealthy. Because of the current government, we are all impoverished.*". Several comments included misspelled words. The parliament speeches were longer, their length varying between 72 and 662 words per speech. The speeches contained a more specialised technical and administrative vocabulary than the social media comments and were formal in style, for example "*subsidies for the purchase of electric and gas cars and distribution infrastructure are necessary actions as we move towards a fossil-free transport system*" and did not contain much informal language, typos or misspellings.

3 Methods

Due to the large amount of research material, I decided to use a combination of automatic text analysis and qualitative methods in the research project, following a similar approach as for example Grimmer & Stewart, 2013; Guetterman et al., 2018 and Jänicke et al., 2015. For this study, I chose to employ two tools that both had Finnish language support but were based on different analysis methodologies, namely Etuma and ChatGPT 4. These tools were

used for extracting keywords from texts and classifying them into specific topics. In this context, the term keyword refers to an expression in the corpus, and topic is a more general category into which keywords are classified. In the Etuma tool, the topics are predefined in the ontology, while in ChatGPT they are based on the patterns it has learned from its training data.

For the comparison of the two methods I adopted, with some modifications, the criteria established by Hillard et al., (2008, p. 33) for an automated classification system that meets the requirements of social scientists. According to their framework, an ideal system for document classification and trend recognition should be 1. Discriminatory: the topics should be mutually exclusive, ensuring clear differentiation between them; 2. Accurate: the topic accurately should reflect the document’s content; 3. Reliable: classification should be consistent between documents, 4. Probabilistic: it should classify secondary topics as well, i.e. have the capability to identify documents that may not primarily focus on the subject in question; and 5. Efficient: it should achieve a high input-benefit ratio.

3.1 Research process

The initial phase of the study started in a zero-shot setting, where no training data or pre-defined categories were used. I analysed the corpus in September 2023 using ChatGPT version 4, accessed through the Poe.com platform, and with Etuma's browser-based NLP tool.

Figure 1 presents the key phases of the research process. During the study, I conducted both distant reading and traditional close reading in parallel (Jänicke et al., 2015; Parks & Peters, 2023). The concept of distant reading was introduced by literary researcher Franco Moretti (2013, p. 45). Moretti's approach aimed to address the inherent challenge humans face in effectively handling a large quantity of texts when limited to reading them on a sentence-by-sentence basis. A similar concept was also discussed by Jockers (2013) through the concepts of micro and macro analysis. The iterative process involves a distant reading phase of automated keyword extraction and topic classification and a close reading phase of examining the context in which the topics and keywords were discussed and validating the results, enabling a deeper understanding of the data. After these phases, the classification is refined to better align with the broader objectives of the research project, ensuring that it captures the relevant information.

Figure 1: Research process.

The approach of combining distant and close reading has been previously employed successfully for example by Guetterman et al. (2018), who conducted a study where they compared the results of qualitative analysis using three different methods: 1) close reading, 2) automatic text analysis, and 3) a combination of the two, by analysing the same materials in separate research groups. Their findings indicated that the combination of traditional close reading and automated distant reading yielded the most comprehensive, high-quality, and detailed results.

In the following sections, I will describe in more detail the special features of the process for both methods separately.

3.2 ChatGPT

The term language model (LM) refers to systems that have been trained to predict the probability of a given token (character, word, or string) (Bender et al., 2021). ChatGPT has been pre-trained on large datasets consisting of web-crawled text, including conversations, and fine-tuned by humans with the Reinforcement Learning from Human Feedback (RLHF) method (OpenAI 2023a).

I employed ChatGPT 4 through the Poe.com platform. Users on this platform can create their own chatbot and customise its settings according to their preferences. This includes configuring a default prompt, which serves as the initial message for the chatbot, as well as setting a temperature value. Increasing the temperature parameter allows the predictive model to take more risks, suggesting less likely alternatives and thereby reducing result consistency (OpenAI 2023b). The prompt plays a central role in determining what kind of results a ChatGPT-powered bot generates. After some testing with different prompt wordings and temperature values, I created a chatbot with the following prompt: "You are an advanced artificial intelligence for text analysis, and you need to classify given texts based on topics. One sentence can contain more than one topic. Extract as many topics as possible. The temperature setting is 0. Format the output to be a simple list of keywords that appear in the text and what topic the keywords are classified into."

During the distant reading phase (Figure 1), I input the texts individually into the same chat conversation and recorded ChatGPT's responses in an Excel table. In the zero-shot setting, the system autonomously identified 47 topics and 935 keywords within the data. Concurrently, I validated the classification by conducting a close reading of the original texts.

In addition, I experimented with a few-shot approach, providing more detailed instructions within the prompt about the specific topics I was interested in. I noticed that the more precise my requirements were defined, the better results I obtained. For instance, prompts like "extract relevant keywords and topics related to commuting" or "how are coronavirus aids and electric car subsidies linked in the texts" produced desired results but demanded accurate information or hypotheses about the material's content. In addition, ChatGPT's memory did not extend very far in the conversation, so it could not answer questions about the entire corpus.

In the third phase of the research process, I employed prompt engineering to refine the results and minimize the potential impact of a poorly formatted prompt on the outcomes by following the instructions of White et al., (2023). Among the four prompt enhancement strategies they proposed, I found "Question refinement" to align best with my needs, although in this case it did not lead to an improvement in recall. A report detailing example chat interactions of the prompt engineering experiment can be found in Appendix 2.

3.3 Etuma

Etuma's technological foundation is rooted in NLP research conducted at the University of Helsinki (Lahtinen, 2000; Tapanainen, 1999), which has since been continued commercially by Etuma (Etuma 2023). Etuma performs several NLP tasks on texts, such as morphological, syntactic, semantic, and sentiment analysis. A key function of Etuma is ontological classification, based on which it groups extracted keywords referring to the same theme into more general categories called topics. For example, the keywords "*electric car*", "*e-car*" and "*battery vehicle*" would be categorised into the same pre-defined topic called Electric cars. It is important to note that although Etuma refers to the classification with the term topic, the method should not be confused with topic modelling methods, which are based on unsupervised machine learning, whereas Etuma employs dictionaries and explicitly defined ontologies.

In this study, I used Etuma's Finnish ontology for the analysis. Etuma's ontology has not been developed for one specific purpose; rather, it has been utilised over time to analyse diverse survey and online data, often catering to the research requirements of companies or public organisations. Through this iterative process, the ontology has gradually evolved. When employing this comprehensive ontology for different research objectives, some level of customisation is typically necessary. The extent of customisation depends on factors such as the nature of the data, the analysis requirements, the specificity of the research topic, and the specialised vocabulary involved.

With Etuma's tool, I followed the same research process described in Figure 1. I first uploaded the original dataset in CSV format into the Etuma analysis system. Within the Etuma interface, I then applied filters as described above, to extract the specific sub-dataset relevant to this research. In the distant reading phase, the system identified 415 topics and 1621 keywords within the data. During the close reading phase, I conducted a review of the most frequently occurring topics and their corresponding keywords. Then I reviewed the less frequent topics that seemed relevant to the research.

The third phase of the process is refining the classification to improve the relevance and precision of the analysis by merging and splitting topics and transferring keywords between them. Etuma has a built-in user interface for these tasks, as refining the classification is an integral part of the research process. The extent of this phase depends on the goals of the research, the amount of material and precision of the classification. After the classification-validation process is completed, new classification rules are updated to the system, with the option that the customised rules can be reused. The purpose of the process is to improve the relevance of the classification to adapt to the specific requirements of the study. However, in

this article I will focus on the zero-shot situation where no fine-tuning has been implemented.

4 Empirical analysis

In this section, I will present the key findings of the comparison between ChatGPT and Etuma. Firstly, I will describe the characteristics of keyword extraction and topic classification for both methods, along with relevant examples. Secondly, I will present a comparison of the methods using a smaller sample, employing traditional metrics such as recall, precision, and F1 score. This analysis will provide a quantitative evaluation of the performance of each method. Additionally, Appendix 1 contains a list of the most frequently occurring topics and keywords identified during the analysis.

4.1 Classification characteristics

Table 1 illustrates the differences in the number of unique keywords and topics identified by each method. The ratio between methods was the same for both corpora, with values rounded to one decimal place (0.1 for topics and 0.6 for keywords), indicating that the text type had no significant effect on the results.

		ChatGPT 4	Etuma
Social media	Keywords	246	435
	Topics	15	144
Parliament speeches	Keywords	722	1311
	Topics	40	378

Table 1: Unique keywords and topics in corpora

Keyword extraction

Both methods successfully analysed the Finnish-language material without significant deficiencies or shortcomings. However, there were differences in the keywords produced by the methods. The most noticeable difference was in the number of keywords: Etuma extracted more than one and a half times the number of unique keywords compared to ChatGPT. Additionally, Etuma tended to have more one-word keywords and ChatGPT generated more multi-word keywords.

The parliamentary speeches contained many acronyms. Both methods correctly classified common abbreviations such as EU (the European Union) and Yle (the Finnish Broadcasting Company). Etuma also extracted some acronyms from the parliamentary speeches (e.g., MAL, KAISU) but did not classify them to an exact topic. Initially, ChatGPT did not recognize these acronyms as keywords. When prompted separately, ChatGPT correctly classified MAL

as "Maankäyttö, asuminen ja liikenne" (Land use, housing and transport) but did not identify "KAISU" as "Keskipitkän aikavälin ilmastopolitiikan suunnitelma" (Medium-term climate change policy plan).

Typos and misspellings are common in social media materials. Etuma provides a list of keywords it does not recognize, and among them, there were 31 unique keywords that were misspelt and thus left uncategorized. Based on my observations, ChatGPT analysed typos correctly more frequently. ChatGPT also correctly classified more names of Members of Parliament (e.g., Li, Tynkkynen) compared to Etuma. However, a detailed analysis of the feature was not conducted in this study.

Topic classification

In terms of unique topics, the difference between Etuma and ChatGPT was even more pronounced, almost tenfold. As can be deduced from the results, ChatGPT tended to employ broader topics (Economy, Politics), while Etuma's classification was more granular (Subsidies, Social security). Furthermore, it is worth noting that some of ChatGPT's unique topics overlapped (e.g., "Economics", "Economics and Finance", "Economy", "Economy and Finance"), leading to even fewer distinct classification themes than the count of unique topic names identified.

I tested various prompts with ChatGPT and repeated identical prompts in new chat interactions, which revealed that classification results for the same piece of text could change even though the content and prompt remained identical. As an example, during the initial analysis round, ChatGPT classified various keywords such as "travelling to Spain" "musicians" and "price range" under the same topic Social issues. However, in a new chat interaction, these same keywords were classified as International travel, Arts/Culture and Economy. This suggests that ChatGPT may have tried to simplify the classification by grouping less precise keywords into a smaller set of topics, indicating an internal learning mechanism guiding the classification.

On a few occasions, ChatGPT demonstrated a behaviour known as hallucination, where it generated information that was not accurate or factual. For example, it stated that "Sulo Vileen" (a character from a Finnish TV series) is a colloquial expression used to refer to ordinary Finns, similar to the term "Joe Public" in English. This occurrence also points to deficiencies in the Finnish training data.

4.2 Validation

To gain a more detailed understanding of the recall and precision levels of the methods, I conducted a comparative analysis with human classification. This involved calculating the traditional metrics of recall, precision, and the F1 score. During the validation phase, I randomly selected a sample of twenty texts from the material, consisting of ten social media posts and ten parliamentary speeches. Then I manually classified the texts by extracting the relevant keywords from them. At this stage, I tagged all potentially interesting keywords in the texts through which it would be possible to examine the material from various perspectives. Similarly, I did not provide specific instructions to Etuma and ChatGPT

regarding the types of keywords to extract, and no domain-specific teaching data or ontology was used for their configuration. As a result, I tagged a total of 151 keywords from the social media sample and 311 keywords from the parliament speech sample.

For each method, I compared the classification results with the human classification and calculated the recall using the following formula:

$$\frac{\textit{relevant extracted keywords}}{\textit{all relevant keywords}}$$

In addition, I calculated precision by reviewing the classification results and determining the number of keywords that were either left unclassified or classified incorrectly. The formula I used to calculate precision is as follows:

$$\frac{\textit{correctly classified keywords}}{\textit{all extracted keywords}}$$

The F1 score, a balanced measure that considers both precision and recall, is calculated as the harmonic mean of the two. I calculated the F1 score using the following formula:

$$2 * \frac{\textit{recall} * \textit{precision}}{\textit{recall} + \textit{precision}}$$

Table 2 presents the recall and precision levels, along with the F1 score that combines both metrics.

		ChatGPT 4	Etuma
Social media	Precision	0.96	0.70
	Recall	0.61	0.85
	F1 score	0.75	0.77
Parliament speeches	Precision	0.96	0.70
	Recall	0.58	0.81
	F1 score	0.72	0.75

Table 2: Recall, precision, and F1 score

Recall

The recall level of Etuma's classification was higher in the social media sample (0.85) than in the parliamentary speech sample (0.81). For a single text, the recall ranged from 0.58 to 1.00, with an average of over 0.80 for both text samples. For ChatGPT the recall varied from 0.42 to 1.00 for individual texts, with an overall recall of 0.61 for the social media sample and 0.58 for the parliamentary speech sample.

A possible explanation for the difference between the two text types is that Etuma's tool is optimized for the analysis of relatively short customer feedback and survey responses, and not for the analysis of longer texts (Etuma 2023). However, also ChatGPT's recall was higher for the social media sample. In the scope of this study, it is difficult to determine whether the difference is only due to the length of the texts, or whether the vocabulary and training materials used in the development of the methods also have an impact. However, I observed that social media posts use more common language terms, while parliamentary speeches have more specialised terms that the tools did not always identify as keywords.

Precision

Etuma's precision rate was 0.70 for both parliamentary speech texts and social media posts. For a single text, the recall ranged from 0.28 to 1.00. However, different things affected the precision rate in the two samples. There were more misspelled words in the social media posts while in parliamentary speeches there was more specialised vocabulary, that Etuma had left unclassified.

ChatGPT's precision rate was higher, 0.96 for both samples, ranging from 0.6 to 1.00 for a single text. Errors typically related to the interpretation of the correct topic, rather than to keyword extraction. For example, from the sentence in a social media post "*With this populist fake news, you can get a few votes in the elections, and nothing else*", ChatGPT classified the keyword "*elections*" (vaalit in Finnish) into a topic called Politics and the keyword "*votes*" (äänet in Finnish) into topic Social issues. The results indicate that the precision of the results obtained is not significantly influenced by the type of text being analysed.

F1 score

The F1 score, which considers both recall and precision, was slightly higher for Etuma in both the social media (0.77 compared to 0.75 for ChatGPT) and parliament speech (0.75 compared to 0.72 for ChatGPT) samples.

5 Discussion

In this section, I revisit the research questions presented in the introduction. I examine the differences between the rule-based ontological classification tool and the LLM chatbot as qualitative content analysis methods and evaluate their characteristics in terms of recall, precision, and efficiency (research question 1). In addition, I discuss how well these methods align with scientific principles, with a particular focus on repeatability, transparency, and

research integrity (research question 2). Table 3 summarizes the results of the comparison, according to the criteria by Hillard et al., (2008) with slight modifications.

	ChatGPT 4	Etuma
Are the topics discriminatory?	No (at least in the zero-shot setting)	Yes
What is the accuracy of the results?	Higher precision in the zero-shot setting	Requires more refining to improve precision
What is the reliability of the results?	Challenges with hallucination, repeatability, and transparency	Higher level of reliability in the zero-shot setting
Are multiple topics identified per document?	Yes	Yes
Is it efficient to implement?	Yes, but training requires computing power	Yes, but refining requires manual work

Table 3: Summary of the method comparison

5.1 Comparison of classification characteristics

Recall

In this study, Etuma's recall was higher compared to that of ChatGPT. The result reveals a fundamental difference between the approaches. ChatGPT focused on the main points and tended to overlook rhetorical expressions and topics mentioned less frequently and more indirectly. A lack of detail was also observed in a previous study when comparing ChatGPT's responses to those of human experts (Guo et al., 2023). In situations where the corpus contains a significant amount of noise or irrelevant data, ChatGPT's ability to emphasise essential information can be beneficial. However, there are scenarios where researchers specifically look for details and rhetorical language, which may not align with ChatGPT's primary focus. In addition, ChatGPT tended to use overlapping and inconsistent topic names. Without pre-defined topic names, the classification does not meet the criterion of discrimination presented by Hillard et al., (2008).

Precision

Precision measured in this study corresponds to the accuracy criterion proposed by (Hillard et al., 2008). As anticipated from prior research (Ortega-Martín et al., 2023), ChatGPT performed well in semantic disambiguation and integrating cultural context into its classification. The adaptability of information related to cultural context stands out as a key strength of LLMs. Spelling mistakes and specialised vocabulary are more challenging for a dictionary-based approach because it is not feasible to add all possible spelling variants and special vocabulary to the ontology. Although both methods may fail to classify certain terms,

abbreviations, and misspelled words based on the vocabularies and training data used, this study revealed that ChatGPT outperformed Etuma in these regards in the zero-shot setting.

In this study, there were no noticeable deficiencies in the knowledge of the Finnish language for either method. While I did not experiment with other languages, it is important to note that analysing a less common language like Finnish might not be as accurate or comprehensive due to the limited training material available.

Efficiency

Hillard et al., (2008) listed efficiency as one of the criteria for a useful classification. An important part of the research process proposed in this article is the validation and fine-tuning of the results in an iterative process. The workload involved in this step depends on the recall and precision of the initial analysis performed by the automated method. Etuma has built-in tools designed to improve recall and precision as it is part of the method's standard process. However, if the precision rate is extremely low, the researcher faces a substantial workload in validating and fine-tuning the classification.

In this study, my attempts to fine-tune ChatGPT's results were not successful, as demonstrated in Appendix 2. However, if employed differently, it may be feasible to fine-tune ChatGPT's classification as well. When evaluating efficiency, it should also be taken into account that LLMs require a lot of computing power, and that the use of open-source alternatives requires GPUs capable of running them.

5.2 Compliance with scientific principles

Reliability

In this study, Hillard and colleagues' (2008) classification reliability criterion is particularly related to repeatability and transparency. The methods differ in terms of repeatability due to their different approaches. With the Etuma tool, the outcome of the analysis remains consistent, unless the researcher alters the classification rules. In contrast, a characteristic of ChatGPT is that identical input can yield different outputs. During this study I noticed that ChatGPT produced different results from the same text using the same prompt, a phenomenon that is in line with findings from earlier research (Ortega-Martín et al., 2023; Reiss, 2023). In this regard, the method resembles qualitative analysis conducted by human analysts, as the classification performed by two different individuals may not be identical. A potential way to address this challenge could involve using similar approaches used to enhance the validity and reliability of human classification, like independently annotating the same material several times and then comparing the results.

The transparency of ChatGPT was hindered by the difficulty of creating a structured classification system that could be easily documented and refined. This posed a challenge in ensuring clear visibility into the inner workings of the model and its decision-making process. ChatGPT operates as more of a black box, while Etuma offers greater transparency due to its classification being built upon predefined dictionaries. The fine-tuning process of Etuma's classification is characterised by transparency and repeatability, as it is largely done manually,

and every change leaves a trace in the system log. However, a challenge emerges from the extensive scope of classification, often requiring researchers to narrow their focus to, for example, a smaller subset of the corpus or the most prevalent topics.

Research integrity

Amid the surrounding technological hype, researchers have a responsibility to ensure that new technologies and tools are not adopted too uncritically for scientific use. For example, various biases and information distortions due to training data and processes, is an area that should be discussed. While these analysis results appeared to be free from evident bias, it is important to acknowledge that in other types of content, biases may emerge. Additionally, ChatGPT's tendency to produce hallucinations as well as its vulnerability to adversarial attacks underscore the need for cautious evaluation of the data it generates. Furthermore, manually validating the analysis of a vast data set can be challenging, potentially allowing misinformation or biases to go unnoticed.

In addition, it is important to consider the implications of these tools on the work of researchers. The findings of this study indicate that LLMs assume a significant portion of decision-making on behalf of researchers. While the idea of reducing workload is appealing, it is important to ensure that the autonomy of researchers is not compromised, potentially impacting the research process and even the results. As an example, an attempt to summarise complex information into broad topics may inadvertently overlook nuances or lead to incorrect interpretations.

From a broader perspective, relying solely on automated analysis tools can potentially direct researchers towards formulating research questions that align with the capabilities of the tools, rather than prioritising a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon being studied. The utilisation of these tools can also be constrained by the fact that certain methods, such as public language models, may not be suitable for analysing sensitive data.

5.3 Strengths and limitations

The study has several strengths. It addresses an existing knowledge gap by exploring the application of an LLM chatbot as a qualitative analysis tool for the study of energy discourse in Finnish using two distinct corpora and comparing the results with a rule-based method. The study offers insights for researchers who are considering employing either a large language model or a rule-based NLP approach for their analysis.

A limitation of the study is that the empirical material is relatively narrow and focused on one specific research topic. Expanding the scope of the study would enhance the generalisability of the findings and provide a more comprehensive understanding of the methods' capabilities. Another limitation is that this study only focused on a zero-shot situation without special training data or ontologies, which would likely have produced different analysis results.

6 Conclusions

Utilisation of ChatGPT as a research tool poses challenges to the reliability of the research due to issues of repeatability and transparency. These challenges arise from the occurrence of hallucinations and potentially from low recall. While Etuma’s approach is to provide a comprehensive description of the content, ChatGPT focuses more on summarising the information, which may result in a lower recall rate. A major limitation related to a low recall rate is that it excessively restricts the researcher's autonomy in decision-making. In this project, my aim was to conduct a comprehensive classification that allows for a qualitative analysis of the material from various perspectives. Therefore, I prefer not to rely on the tool to make determinations about what is important or interesting in the text on my behalf.

On the other hand, a limitation of the rule-based approach often lies in its lack of flexibility when it comes to interpreting semantic meaning and context. This shortcoming could be addressed through specialized ontologies and refining, which, at least with the tools employed in this study, proves to be more straightforward with a rule-based method.

6.1 Implications for future research

In scientific research, repeatability and transparency are important features and the classification of qualitative content should be consistent and accurate. While ChatGPT may not yet surpass rule-based NLP methods in all these respects, it has undeniable strengths such as accurate semantic analysis and information of cultural contexts.

In future research, it would be interesting to employ the methods in parallel and leverage the strengths of both. During my research, I had some preliminary ideas for integrating the methods, as depicted by a dashed line in Figure 2. The objective would be to utilise LLM in a manner that ensures its shortcomings do not compromise the scientific principles, for example in the following ways.

Figure 2: Research process combining rule-based and LLM approaches.

Firstly, leveraging the LLM's capacity for semantic interpretations could enhance the semantic classification of another NLP method in the zero-shot phase, assisting in semantic filtering of research material based on the studied phenomenon.

Secondly, in the close reading phase, LLM could aid researchers by generating automated summaries or in interpreting ambiguous or complex texts, suggesting alternative meanings and context to researchers in the validation process. The knowledge within the LLM based on the vast training data could extend beyond the corpus, aiding in interpreting the discourse in the broader social context, for instance.

Finally, in the classification refinement phase, LLM's ability to identify semantic meanings and its creative capabilities could be used to formulate new topics or ontologies based on the feedback from the validation process. This approach aligns with the partially automated ontology learning process, which has been discussed for example by Khadir et al., (2021). By merging concepts and terminology from diverse sources, such as social media and parliamentary speeches, this ontology could have the potential to establish a comprehensive and versatile framework for analysis that compensates for certain shortcomings and enhances the overall effectiveness of the classification approach. In my project, this development will continue, as I apply the methods to analyse new energy discourse materials.

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A Appendices

Appendix 1 Most frequent topics and keywords

Ranking	ChatGPT 4 topic and frequency	ChatGPT 4 keywords (translated into English)	Etuma topic and frequency	Etuma keywords (translated into English)
1.	Economy (n=53)	"wealthy", "electric car subsidy", "public spending"	Subsidies (n=72)	"electric car subsidy", "coronavirus aid"
2.	Politics (n=53)	"government", "left-wing", "vote"	Cars (n=42)	"Electric car", "car"
3.	Social Issues (n=41)	"rural areas", "economic hardship", "social and health services"	Government Organizations (n=34)	"government", "EU", "IMF"
4.	Environment (n=27)	"forest conservation", "nature restoration", "swamps"	Fuel (n=20)	"fuel", "gasoline", "diesel"
5.	Automotive Industry (n=18)	"electric car subsidy", "internal combustion engine", "electric car"	Prices (n=19)	"price", "expensive", "cheap"
6.	Energy (n=14)	"electricity prices", "energy prices", "fossil fuels"	Purchasing (n=18)	"buy"
7.	Transportation (n=12)	"fuel taxation", "electric car use", "diesel cars"	Energy (n=15)	"electricity", "energy"
8.	Economics (n=8)	"fuel tax", "transportation costs", "costs"	Payments (n=14)	"pay"
9.	Society (n=8)	"mail delivery", "public transportation", "accessible cars"	Taxes (n=12)	"taxes"
10.	Agriculture (n=7)	"agriculture", "food producers", "grain"	Income (n=11)	"low income", "high income"
11.	Infrastructure (n=7)	"basic route maintenance", "development project costs"	Climate Change (n=9)	"climate change"
12.	Economics and Finance (n=6)	"acquisition support", "date of purchase"	Debt (n=9)	"debt", "national debt"
13.	Industry (n=6)	"game companies"	Social Security (n=8)	"child benefit", "state aid"
14.	Energy and Environment (n=5)	"climate actions", "energy self-sufficiency", "energy crisis"	Wealthy (n=6)	"wealthy"
15.	Policy and Planning (n=5)	"support procedure", "steering mechanisms", "goals"	Saving (n=5)	"saving"

Chat interaction 1

Researcher	<i>“In the scope of text classification, suggest a better question that would allow me to get the most accurate classification of all possible keywords and topics that appear in the texts I provide.”</i>
ChatGPT 4	<i>“Given the following text, could you please identify and categorize all the keywords and topics present? Please provide a detailed breakdown of each keyword and topic and explain why each keyword or topic falls into its respective category based on the context of the text.”</i>
Researcher	<i>“Here is the text to be classified: [a social media comment from the corpus]”</i>

Result: One less keyword was extracted, and two additional topics were uncovered in the results following prompt engineering. Similar results were obtained with another social media comment and two parliamentary speeches.

Chat interaction 2

Researcher	<i>“In the scope of text classification, suggest a better question that would allow me to get the most accurate classification of all possible keywords and topics that appear in the texts I provide.”</i>
ChatGPT 4	<i>“Sure, here's a revised version of your question: "Given a set of texts, could you please perform a keyword extraction and topic classification? For each text, provide a list of extracted keywords along with their corresponding topic categories. The output should be formatted as a list where each entry includes the keyword and its associated topic category.””</i>
Researcher	<i>“Given a set of texts, could you please perform a keyword extraction and topic classification? For each text, provide a list of extracted keywords along with their corresponding topic categories. The output should be formatted as a list where each entry includes the keyword and its associated topic category.”</i>
ChatGPT	<i>“I'm sorry for any confusion, but as a text-based AI model, I don't have the capability to process a set of texts in real-time or perform keyword extraction and topic classification on a large dataset. However, I can certainly guide you on how you might approach this task using various natural language processing (NLP) techniques. Here's a general approach you might consider: Text Preprocessing: This involves cleaning the text by removing punctuation, converting all text to lowercase, removing stop words (common words like 'and', 'the', 'is', etc.), and stemming/lemmatization (reducing words to their root form). Keyword Extraction: There are several techniques for keyword extraction, including TF-IDF (Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency), TextRank,</i>

and RAKE (Rapid Automatic Keyword Extraction). These methods can help identify the most important words in each text.

Topic Classification: Once you have the keywords, you can use them to classify the topics. One common approach is Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA), which is a type of probabilistic model that assumes each document is a mixture of a certain number of topics.

The output of this process could be a list where each entry includes the keyword and its associated topic category. For example:

- Keyword: 'climate', Topic: 'Environment'
- Keyword: 'election', Topic: 'Politics'
- Keyword: 'AI', Topic: 'Technology'

Please note that this is a simplified explanation of the process and actual implementation might require a deeper understanding of NLP and machine learning techniques."

Result: No keywords or topics.

Chat interaction 3

Researcher	<i>"Given a set of texts, could you please perform a keyword extraction and topic classification? For each text, provide a list of extracted keywords along with their corresponding topic categories. The output should be formatted as a list where each entry includes the keyword and its associated topic category."</i>
ChatGPT 4	<i>"Sure, I can certainly help with that. However, I need some example texts to work with. Could you please provide some?"</i>
Researcher	<i>"Here is the text: [a social media comment from the corpus]"</i>

Result: Two more keywords extracted, and two fewer topics compared to the previous classification.